

Angle of Attack Based on Air Combat Maneuvering Instrumentation

Jean Marcel Knapp dos Santos

ABSTRACT

This paper discusses a method of determining the angle of attack of an aircraft based on its Air Combat Maneuvering Instrumentation. Based on the aircraft current geographic location and its height, its pitch, heading and roll, and its next recorded geographic location and heights, its possible to transform it through trigonometry to determine the angle of attack, without the need to measure air flow, increasing the feedback of the aircraft and pilot performances at the debriefing.

INTRODUCTION

As a wing moves through the air, the wing is inclined to the flight direction at some angle. The angle of attack is the angle between the chord line and the flight path (NASA, 2021). To illustrate this, lets consider MAC an indicator of the Mean Aerodynamic Chord and FP an indicator of the Flight Path.

Figure 1 - Angle of attack and related angles.

Source: The author (2021).

The MAC is projected horizontally by the aircraft heading, which is the horizontal angle of the aircraft fuselage vector relative to the geographic north (Skybrary, 2019), and vertically by the aircraft pitch, which is the vertical angle of the aircraft fuselage vector relative to the horizon (Aeroskytech).

The FP is projected horizontally by the aircraft tracking, which is the horizontal angle of the aircraft movement vector relative to the geographic north (Skybrary, 2019), and vertically by the aircraft slope, which is the vertical angle of the aircraft movement vector relative to the horizon (Aeroskytech).

DEVELOPMENT

To determine the angle of attack, we need to project the Mean Aerodynamic Chord (MAC) along the aircraft lateral axis until it aligns with the Flight Path (FP) along the aircraft vertical axis. The angle difference between them in the vertical axis will be the angle of attack.

To calculate the slope angle, we take compare the distance and height difference of the current aircraft position and its next recorded position. The slope angle will be the arctangent of the height difference and the distance:

Equation 1 - Slope angle based on the height difference and distance.

$$slope = \arctan \left(\frac{heightDiff}{distance} \right)$$

Source: The author (2021).

Figure 2 - Representation of distance, height difference, pitch and slope.

Source: The author (2021).

Figure 3 - Representation of heading and tracking.

Source: The author (2021).

To calculate A, according to Figure 1, we compare the aircraft heading (yaw of the fuselage) and the tracking (yaw of the flight path) to the next recorded position. A will be the difference between the two angles:

Equation 2 - A based on tracking and heading.

$$A = tracking - heading$$

Source: The author (2021).

To calculate B, according to Figure 1, we calculate the opposite side of the roll angle, with the opposite side being A:

Equation 3 - B based on A and roll.

$$B = slip \times \tan(roll)$$

Source: The author (2021).

To calculate C, according to Figure 1, we subtract the slope and A from the pitch:

Equation 4 - B based on pitch, slope and A.

$$C = pitch - slope - A$$

Source: The author (2021).

The angle of attack α will be the adjacent side of the roll angle, with the hypotenuse being B:

Equation 5 - Angle of attack based on B and roll.

$$\alpha = B \times \cos(roll)$$

Source: The author (2021).

CONCLUSION

It's possible to calculate the aircraft angle of attack without wind flow information, only by transforming the aircraft movement vector and its position vector, providing useful data for debriefings.

REFERENCES

Aeroskytech. Notions and basics. *Aeroskytech*. [Online] [Cited: 15 September 2021.] <https://www.aeroskytech.com/english/firstnotions/firstnotions.html>.

NASA. 2021. Inclination Effects on Lift. *Glenn Research Center*. [Online] 13 May 2021. [Cited: 15 September 2021.] <https://www.grc.nasa.gov/WWW/k-12/airplane/incline.html>.

Skybrary. 2019. Heading, Track and Radial. *Skybrary*. [Online] 4 March 2019. [Cited: 15 September 2021.] https://www.skybrary.aero/index.php/Heading,_Track_and_Radial.